

1 **Long-term operation of a pilot-scale anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) treating**
2 **high salinity low loaded municipal wastewater in real environment**

3

4 Alessia Foglia¹, Çağrı Akyol^{1*}, Nicola Frison², Evina Katsou³, Anna Laura Eusebi^{1*},
5 Francesco Fatone¹

6

7 ¹ *Department of Science and Engineering of Materials, Environment and Urban Planning-*
8 *SIMAU, Faculty of Engineering, Marche Polytechnic University, 60131, Ancona, Italy*

9 ² *Department of Biotechnology, University of Verona, 37134, Verona, Italy*

10 ³ *Department of Civil Engineering and Environmental Engineering, Institute of Environment,*
11 *Health and Societies, Brunel University London, Uxbridge Campus, Middlesex, UB8 3PH,*
12 *Uxbridge, United Kingdom*

13

14

15

16

17

18

19

20

21

22

23 * Corresponding author (Ç. Akyol)

24 E-mail: c.akyol@staff.univpm.it

25 Tel: +39 071 2204911 Fax: +39 071 2204729

1 **Abstract**

2 Long term operation of an anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) treating municipal
3 wastewater was investigated in a real seawater intrusion spot in Falconara Marittima (Central
4 Italy) on the Adriatic coastline. Changes in biological conversion and system stability were
5 determined with respect to varying organic loading rate (OLR) and high salinity conditions. At
6 an OLR of $1 \text{ kgCOD}\cdot\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$, biogas production was around $0.39 \pm 0.2 \text{ L}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$. The increase of
7 the OLR to $2 \text{ kgCOD}\cdot\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$ resulted in the increase of biogas production to $2.8 \pm 1.5 \text{ L}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$
8 (with $33.6\% \pm 10.5\%$ of CH_4) with methanol addition and to $4.11 \pm 3.1 \text{ L}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$ (with $29.7\% \pm$
9 11.8% of CH_4) with fermented cellulosic sludge addition. COD removal by the AnMBR was
10 $83\% \pm 1\%$ when the effluent COD concentration was below $100 \text{ mg O}_2\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The addition of the
11 fermented sludge affected the membrane operation; significant fouling occurred after long-term
12 filtration, where the trans-membrane pressure (TMP) reached up to 500 mbar. Citric acid
13 solution was applied to remove scalants and the TMP reached the initial value. High saline
14 conditions of $1500 \text{ mgCl}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ adversely affected the biogas production without deteriorating the
15 membrane operation. The treated effluent met the EU quality standards of the D.M. 185/2003
16 and the new European Commission Resolution for reuse in agriculture.

17 **Keywords:** AnMBR; membrane fouling; municipal wastewater; fermentation; salinity;
18 cellulosic sludge

19

20 **Nomenclature**

21 AD: Anaerobic Digestion

22 AeMBR: Aerobic Membrane Bioreactor

23 AnMBR: Anaerobic Membrane Bioreactor

24 CAS: Conventional Activated Sludge

25 COD: Chemical Oxygen Demand

- 1 DO: Dissolved Oxygen
- 2 EC: Electrical Conductivity
- 3 EPS: Extracellular Polymeric Substances
- 4 HRT: Hydraulic Retention Time
- 5 MLSS: Mixed Liquor Suspended Solids
- 6 MWT: Municipal Wastewater Treatment
- 7 OLR: Organic Loading Rate
- 8 ORP: Oxidation Reduction Potential
- 9 PE: Population Equivalent
- 10 sCOD: Soluble Chemical Oxygen Demand
- 11 SMA: Specific Methanogenic Activity
- 12 SRT: Sludge Retention Time
- 13 SuMBR: Submerged Membrane Bioreactor
- 14 tCOD: Total Chemical Oxygen Demand
- 15 TKN: Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen
- 16 TMP: Trans Membrane Pressure
- 17 TN: Total Nitrogen
- 18 TP: Total Phosphorus
- 19 TS: Total Solids
- 20 TSS: Total Suspended Solids
- 21 UASB: Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket
- 22 VFA: Volatile Fatty Acid
- 23 VS: Volatile Solids
- 24 WWTP: Wastewater Treatment Plant
- 25

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Anaerobic treatment in high-rate bioreactors has increased in number of applications during
3 municipal wastewater treatment (MWT) in the last decade while presenting an advanced
4 technology for environmental protection and resource preservation [1,2]. The combination of
5 membrane and an anaerobic bioreactor (Anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR)) paved the
6 way for a sustainable wastewater treatment with complete biomass retention, and with
7 additional advantages such as less sludge production, high quality effluent and net energy
8 production as the organic matter is converted into high-value products (volatile fatty acids
9 (VFAs)) and energy in the form of biogas [3,4]. These advantages of anaerobic treatment
10 systems result in a decrease in operational costs compared to conventional wastewater treatment
11 plants (WWTPs) that often include aerobic processes (i.e. conventional activated sludge (CAS)
12 or aerobic membrane bioreactor (AeMBR)) [5–7].

13 Sludge bed-based technologies, such as upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactors, have
14 been widely used for MWT in full-scale WWTPs especially in tropical regions [8–10]. The
15 AnMBRs, on the other hand, have been mainly applied for the treatment of high strength
16 industrial wastewater [1,11]. Currently, emphasis has been given to adapt AnMBRs in MWT
17 to simultaneously recover energy and clean water [12,13]. In fact, AnMBRs are suitable for the
18 treatment of low-loaded wastewater due to the complete retention of slow-growing
19 methanogens and thus have the potential to operate at higher organic loading rates (OLR)
20 [14,15]. Applied OLRs in AnMBRs range from $0.3 \text{ kgCOD}\cdot\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$ to $12.5 \text{ kgCOD}\cdot\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$
21 during the treatment of municipal wastewater [4,16]. From this point of view, further research
22 is still required to optimize the application of AnMBRs in MWT with respect to different
23 feeding characteristics that can help to assess the overall performance of AnMBRs at varying
24 OLRs.

1 The application of AnMBRs in coastal regions is also another point that lacks sufficient
2 information in the literature for a successful WWTP operation. In coastal regions, variable
3 salinity of wastewater occurs due to seawater infiltration to sewers or introduction of saline
4 water from industrial processes such as seafood and cheese production [12,17]. In general, the
5 salinity effect in anaerobic processes can cause two main critical operational problems. Firstly,
6 increased salinity results in deterioration of membrane filtration and fouling aspects due also to
7 the decrease of the biomass particle size. For instance, salinity increase from 8 to 20 gNa⁺.L⁻¹ to
8 20 gNa⁺.L⁻¹ was accompanied by the increase of the transmembrane pressure (TMP) up to 350
9 mbar, while a ten-fold reduction in biomass particle size resulted in a filtration resistance
10 increase [18]. Similarly, Yurtsever et al. [19] indicated that salinity induced large molecules, to
11 be detected as foulants in gel/cake layer; they may originate from biomass loosely bound
12 extracellular polymeric substances (EPS). Secondly, saline conditions can suppress microbial
13 growth and cause the disintegration of flocs and granules that further lead prominent biomass
14 wash-out affecting the sludge granulation [20].

15 The advantages of AnMBRs in MWT are evident with respect to the necessity of low-cost
16 energy technologies in WWTPs; however, long-term operational experiences in coastal regions
17 are not fully recognized. The main motivation of this study was therefore to investigate the
18 treatment efficiency of low-loaded wastewater in combined sewers by AnMBR and to
19 determine the optimal operating conditions with respect to varying OLRs by using fermented
20 cellulosic sludge rich in VFAs. In this aspect, a pilot-scale UASB coupled with anaerobic
21 ultrafiltration membranes was operated with real influent in a coastal area that is considered
22 hotspot for seawater intrusion, Falconara Marittima WWTP, Italy. The effect of seawater
23 intrusion in biological activity and membrane filtration of municipal wastewater in coastal areas
24 was further elaborated in the specifically-designed integrated treatment scheme. Since the

1 majority of first generation MBRs was implemented in northern Europe, the presented results
2 may offer options to a critical part of the MBR market.

3 **2. Materials and methods**

4 **2.1. Full scale plant in Falconara area**

5 The pilot plant is located in the WWTP of Falconara Marittima (coastal area hotspot for
6 seawater intrusion) (**Figure 1**) and fed with the real influent of the full-scale plant. The WWTP
7 of Falconara Marittima (Italy) has a design treatment capacity of 80,000 PE with nominal
8 influent flow rate of 30,000 m³·d⁻¹. After screening, degritting and primary settling, the
9 wastewater is biologically treated with CAS that is operated with two identical parallel lines
10 applying the Modified Ludzack Ettinger scheme. The total volume of the biological
11 compartment is 13,700 m³, divided into 8,860 m³ and 4,900 m³ for denitrification and
12 nitrification compartments, respectively. The aerated compartments are equipped
13 by ceramic fine bubble diffusers. The Falconara Marittima WWTP is continuously monitored
14 by online sensors (Dissolved Oxygen (DO); temperature; mixed liquor suspended solids
15 (MLSS) and oxidation reduction potential (ORP)) and magnetic flow meters
16 (influent, effluent, recirculation and waste sludge). The average sludge retention time (SRT) is
17 10 days and the sludge recycle ratio ($Q_{\text{sludge recycled}}/Q_{\text{influent}}$) is 0.5.

18 The Falconara Marittima WWTP is controlled by the European Environment Agency
19 (www.eea.europa.eu, 2017), since it is located in a coastal area. Since it is a hotspot for
20 infiltrations from groundwater and marine intrusions, low-loading wastewater occurs in the
21 WWTP influent during the dry weather conditions. The average quality of the raw influent is
22 given in **Table 1**; where the values reveal that the influent is characterized by high chloride
23 concentration around $334 \pm 236 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ as a result of the seawater intrusion.

24 **2.2. Pilot plant in Falconara Marittima**

1 Following the preliminary treatment (screening, degritting and oils removal), pretreated
2 influent from Falconara WWTP was sent to a pilot-scale UASB coupled with an anaerobic
3 ultrafiltration membrane. To evaluate the long-term stability period, the experimental work was
4 conducted for 480 days with real wastewater influent. As shown in **Figure 2**, different phases
5 were designed by increasing the influent organic loading testing the following configurations:
6 a) urban wastewater, b) co-treatment of urban wastewater and methanol, c) co-treatment of
7 urban wastewater and fermentation liquid.

8 A steady influent flow rate of about $3 \text{ L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ of wastewater and the external addition of methanol
9 and fermented sludge were achieved by peristaltic pumps (Watson-Marlow, UK). The first one
10 was able to guarantee a flow rate of $15 \text{ L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, the second and the third was $3 \text{ L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ - $10 \text{ L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and
11 $15 \text{ L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively.

12 The UASB was a cylindrical Plexiglas reactor (16 L) with an internal diameter of 15 cm and a
13 total height of 136 cm. The reactor was divided into two compartments: the first was the real
14 reaction chamber at the bottom (85 cm, 12.4 L), while the second, on the top, was a tri-phase
15 separator (GLS) with 21.9 cm height and was connected to a hydraulic guard which created the
16 appropriate backpressure for the biogas release. The temperature of the UASB reactor was kept
17 constant (30°C) by applying internal and external windings with hot water at 45°C . The
18 produced biogas was measured by a milligas counter (Ritter, Germany). The hydraulic retention
19 time (HRT) was maintained at 5-6 h. The up-flow velocity of the UASB reactor was maintained
20 at $1 \text{ m}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. The UASB reactor was inoculated with the sludge obtained from a paper mill WWTP
21 in Castelfranco Veneto (Italy).

22 The UASB effluent was collected in a mixed reactor equipped with pH and temperature probes
23 and it was partially recirculated in the UASB reactor (internal recirculation) and partially sent
24 by gravity to the second unit (anaerobic ultrafiltration tank). The performance of anaerobic
25 process was monitored throughout the experimental period with respect to OLR, indicator α ,

1 specific methanogenic activity (SMA), upflow speed and biogas production. The UASB was
2 followed by anaerobic hollow-fiber ultrafiltration membrane (PURON® Koch membrane
3 system, with 0.03 μm of nominal pore-size, a total nominal surface 0.5 m^2 , 0.25 m height)
4 installed in a Plexiglas reactor (0.29 m x 0.7 m x 0.39 m) and equipped with level and TMP
5 sensors.

6 **2.3. Experimental periods for UASB and AnMBR**

7 Different OLRs (ranging from 1 $\text{kgCOD}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$ to 2 $\text{kgCOD}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$) were studied and
8 controlled based on the influent flow. All experimental periods, applied configurations and
9 operational parameters are summarized in **Table 2**. In Period 1 only raw wastewater was treated
10 by UASB at 30 °C, while the co-treatment of raw wastewater and methanol was tested in Period
11 2. Period 2 was divided in 3 sub-periods: In Period 2.1, mixture of raw wastewater and methanol
12 was treated only by UASB at 30 °C. In Period 2.2, the co-treatment of raw wastewater and
13 methanol was conducted at 30°C UASB + ambient AnMBR; whereas, the same configuration
14 of Period 2.2 was applied in Period 2.3 except that the temperature of AnMBR was also kept at
15 30 °C. In Period 3, the wastewater was co-treated with the supernatant of fermented cellulosic
16 sludge in UASB + AnMBR. During Period 3, the raw wastewater was filtered by dynamic
17 rotating primary unit (SALSNES FS1000) to recover cellulosic sludge [21]. The separated
18 sludge was then sent to anaerobic fermentation reactor (1400 L) operating at 30°C in
19 uncontrolled pH. The fermented flow was dewatered (BABY 2 PIERALISI) and the liquid
20 supernatant was used to increase the OLR of UASB reactor up to 2 $\text{kgCOD}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$. Finally,
21 during the fermentation liquid co-treatment, NaCl solution was added in the UASB reactor to
22 simulate high saline conditions in Period 4. Chloride concentration was increased gradually
23 from 200 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to 500 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ during first 50 days and then to 1500 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ after 50 days and
24 the maximum of 2200 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ at the end. The main characteristics of the influents are reported
25 in **Table 3**.

1 The performance of the system was investigated in terms of organic content removal and biogas
2 production with respect to above-listed configurations (Periods 1-2-3-4). The indicator α , that
3 is defined as the ratio of partial alkalinity over total alkalinity, was measured to verify the
4 stability of the biological process. An upflow velocity of $0.7 \text{ m}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ to $1 \text{ m}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ was maintained to
5 keep the sludge blanket in suspension.

6 **2.4. Functional characterization of AnMBR**

7 Preliminary tests were carried out to optimize the AnMBR membrane pilot-scale before being
8 coupled with UASB. The start-up conditions of the AnMBR are given in **E-Supplementary**
9 **material**. The critical flux of the AnMBR was studied through step-flux method and 6 steps of
10 10 minutes have been tested for 60 minutes. The pump was set up in order to increase the flux
11 rate and TMP was recorded. The critical flux was $12\text{-}14 \text{ L}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and for all the experimental
12 periods membrane flux was maintained below this value. Moreover, the effect of the solid
13 concentration range ($0\text{-}10 \text{ mgMLSS}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, $30\text{-}50 \text{ mgMLSS}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, $80\text{-}100 \text{ mgMLSS}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and 300
14 $\text{mgMLSS}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) in the membrane fouling was assessed. The effect of gas sparging in the fouling
15 rate was evaluated at different solid concentrations with and without gas-sparging to investigate
16 the effect of gas bubbles in terms of membrane fouling and operative TMP values. The gas-
17 sparging method adopted in these tests, using nitrogen gas (N_2) for 10 seconds off (gas off) and
18 10 seconds on (gas on), with a specific flow rate value of $2 \text{ m}^3\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ [22]. Moreover, gas-
19 sparging frequency was studied. The results showed that the increase of the gas sparging
20 frequency increased the percentage of degassing methane; and the degassing methane from gas-
21 sparging could be recovered (see **E-Supplementary material**).

22 For each experimental set, the temperature was measured at the beginning and at the end of the
23 test. The temperature was normalized at 20°C using the Arrhenius equation. For each flux (J)
24 ranging from 6 LMH to 22 LMH, the average TMP (TMP_{ave}) and the slope ($d\text{TMP}/dt$) were
25 calculated (**E-Supplementary material**). The TMP reached up to $0.79 \text{ mbar}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ at MLSS

1 concentration of 300 mgMLSS·L⁻¹ without gas sparging. Differently, for the same MLSS
2 concentration, the TMP was maintained below 0.1 mbar·min⁻¹ by switching on the gas sparging.
3 Therefore, the gas sparging decreasing the fouling rate independently from the MLSS
4 concentrations and the preliminary tested gas sparging durations were adopted for the long
5 operating periods.

6 Granulometric characterizations of the influent of AnMBR was conducted to characterize the
7 particle size of influent solids. Accumulative volume percent was calculated. Diameters d₅₀ and
8 d₉₀ of particles were found to be 14 μm and 58 μm, respectively.

9 Membrane cleaning was performed by adding hypochlorite solution at 14% w/v (200 ppm)
10 every 45 days to remove organic fouling of the membrane; while NaOCl at a concentration of
11 1000 mg·L⁻¹ or citric acid (C₆H₈O₇) at 1000 mg·L⁻¹ was used to restore the initial permeability
12 of the membrane. Permeability tests were carried out with tap water and TMP values were
13 measured at different steps of permeation flow rate. Following the preliminary tests, the
14 AnMBR reactor was fed with UASB effluent in different Periods (**Table 2**) and coupled with
15 UASB as mentioned earlier.

16 **2.5. Analytical methods**

17 Standard analyses were conducted in the influent flow, the UASB effluent and the membrane
18 permeate twice a week. All the samples were analyzed in terms of pH, chemical oxygen
19 demand (COD), total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), ammonia nitrogen (NH₄⁺-N), soluble COD
20 (sCOD), nitrate nitrogen (NO₃-N) and nitrite nitrogen (NO₂-N) according to Standard Methods
21 [23]. The sCOD was measured in the filtrate obtained after the filtration of the sample through
22 0.45 μm Whatman membrane filters. NO₂-N, NO₃-N were measured by ion chromatography
23 (Dionex DX120) in samples that were first filtered through 0.45 μm Whatman membrane
24 filters.

1 Moreover, in each period, anaerobic biomass was sampled from UASB reactor to investigate
2 SMA (data not shown) at different OLRs according to the experimental method reported by
3 Hussain et al. [24]. Acetate (solution of 2 gCOD·L⁻¹, with a ratio VS/COD of 2) was used and
4 its degree of conversion into methane was normalized considering the volatile solids (VS) and
5 expressed in m³CH₄·kgVS⁻¹·d⁻¹. The CH₄ content of the biogas was analyzed by a Brüel and
6 Kjaer Multi-gas Monitor Type 1302, based on photoacoustic spectroscopy. During the periods
7 with methanol and fermentation liquid addition, extracellular polymeric substances (EPS)
8 were also analyzed according to the method found in Zhang et al. [25].

9 **2.6. Statistical analysis**

10 Principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to the dataset to identify the relationships
11 between the applied operating conditions and system performance. The obtained loadings of
12 the variables in each principal component (**see E-Supplementary material**) mapped their
13 relationship with the respective principal component (PC). The scores of the principal
14 components mapped the different samples in the new dimensional space of the principal
15 components that simplified the investigation of the different relationships between the
16 variables. The first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) were then selected for further
17 interpretation of the results. More information on the PCA can be found in [26].

18 **3. Results and discussion**

19 **3.1. Characterization and variability of the influent**

20 The main characteristics of the influent for each operational period is given in **Table 3**. pH of
21 the influent remained almost stable (7.5 - 7.8). The total alkalinity of the influent ranged from
22 281 ± 92 mgCaCO₃·L⁻¹ to 526 ± 110 mgCaCO₃·L⁻¹, with the highest concentration observed in
23 Period 3. EC was 1464 ± 153 ms/cm and 1467 ± 380 ms/cm in Period 1 and Period 2
24 respectively, while the addition the fermentation liquid increased the EC to 1817 ± 350 ms·cm⁻¹
25 ¹ in Period 3. Saline conditions in Period 4 increased further the EC up to 2787 ± 1300 ms·cm⁻¹

1 ¹. Cl⁻ concentration of the influent was 282 ± 126 mg·L⁻¹, 304 ± 300 mg·L⁻¹, 393 ± 377 mg·L⁻¹
2 and 1100 ± 618 mg·L⁻¹ during Periods 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively. COD concentrations were 207
3 ± 73 mg·L⁻¹, 388 ± 80 mg·L⁻¹, 375 ± 148 mg·L⁻¹ and 550±330 mg·L⁻¹ in Periods 1,2,3 and 4,
4 respectively. Meanwhile, the average sCOD concentration was 50 mg·L⁻¹ in Period 1 and in the
5 range of 242-297 mg·L⁻¹ in Periods 2, 3 and 4. The addition of methanol and fermentation liquid
6 increased the soluble organic fraction of the influent. On the other hand, the soluble organic
7 fraction in the influent decreased due to the saline conditions occurred in Period 4. NH₄⁺-N
8 concentration was 22±6 mg·L⁻¹, 20.5±6 mg·L⁻¹, 61±33 mg·L⁻¹ and 30±10 mg·L⁻¹ in Periods 1, 2,
9 3 and 4, respectively. The highest influent TP and PO₄-P concentrations were observed in
10 Period 3, while the highest TSS concentration was recorded in Period 4. The results are in line
11 with existing literature that were reported for typical real municipal wastewater, except for
12 parameters such as EC, TSS, Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ that were measured comparatively higher due to
13 seawater intrusion in the WWTP of Falconara Marittima [3,5,27].

14 **3.2. Start-up period of UASB**

15 The UASB reactor was inoculated with anaerobic sludge (granular sludge TS = 2.72%, VS/TS
16 = 74%; flocculent sludge TS = 1.42%, VS/TS = 60%) taken from a paper mill WWTP in
17 Castelfranco Veneto, Italy. The temperature of the UASB was increased gradually to 30°C after
18 10 days of operation period. The reactor operated for 5 months at 30°C with OLR value of 1.05
19 ± 0.4 kgCOD·m³⁻¹·d⁻¹. The flow rate was maintained between at 3.38 ± 0.6 L·h⁻¹. Meanwhile, α
20 was between 0.12 and 0.43, which indicated a stable biological process. The average biogas
21 production was 0.39 ± 0.2 Lbiogas·d⁻¹. The COD and TSS removal efficiencies were 63% and
22 84%, respectively. In addition, 86% of P and N were released during the start-up period of
23 UASB.

24 **3.3. Effect of OLR in the system performance**

1 Following the start-up period, the UASB was first fed with the mixture of municipal wastewater
2 and methanol (as the external C source) and the OLR was increased to $2.1 \pm 0.6 \text{ kgCOD m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$
3 1 (Period 2). The flow rate was maintained at $2.98 \pm 0.3 \text{ L h}^{-1}$. The variations in OLR and α
4 value throughout the operation period are given in **Figure 3a** and **Figure 3b**, respectively. α
5 value remained almost stable in the beginning of Period 2, and then tended to increase up to
6 0.65. while 86% P and 88% N were released. The average biogas production increased to $2.8 \pm$
7 $1.5 \text{ L biogas d}^{-1}$ with $33.6\% \pm 10.5\%$ of CH_4 in Period 2. The COD and TSS removal efficiencies
8 of the UASB was 70% and 48% respectively while the application of the AnMBR increased
9 the average COD and TSS removal to 85%, and $> 99.99\%$. On the other hand, the release of P
10 and N in the UASB was 86% P and 88% N and then slightly decreased to 76% and 83% in the
11 integrated UASB+AnMBR configuration, respectively.

12 In Period 3, α value was between 0.16 and 0.52 with an average of 0.29 ± 0.1 . The addition of
13 the fermentation liquid in the influent resulted in a peak in the biogas production; while only
14 9% CH_4 was measured indicating excess CO_2 production via fermentation (**Figure 4**). The
15 biogas production started to increase gradually together with the CH_4 content of the biogas.
16 Hence, up to $10.25 \text{ L biogas d}^{-1}$ was generated with 51.9% of CH_4 (average of 4.11 ± 3.1
17 L biogas d^{-1} with $29.7\% \pm 11.8\%$ of CH_4). The addition of fermentation liquid as the external
18 carbon source increased the biogas production without affecting the overall CH_4 content of the
19 biogas. In Period 3, the COD removal efficiencies were 42% and 83% in UASB and
20 UASB+AnMBR, respectively. The TSS removal efficiencies in UASB and UASB+AnMBR
21 were 38% and 100%, respectively, while P and N releases were 85% and 75%, respectively.

22 The application of the AnMBR in the study of Gouveia et al. [2] for the treatment of municipal
23 wastewater under psychrophilic conditions and loading rate of 2 and $2.5 \text{ kgCOD m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$
24 resulted in effluent tCOD concentrations of 100 mg L^{-1} – 120 mg L^{-1} . In another study by Wei
25 et al. [28], a wide range of volumetric OLR (0.8 – $10 \text{ gCOD L}^{-1}\text{d}^{-1}$) was tested in AnMBR to treat

1 synthetic municipal wastewater. The results showed that at steady conditions, 98% COD
2 removal was achieved while the application of high sludge OLR led to high methane production
3 of over 300 mL·gCOD⁻¹. Wijekoon et al. [29] tested the performance of a thermophilic AnMBR
4 at different OLRs ranging from 5.12 kgCOD·m³·d⁻¹ to 12 kgCOD·m³·d⁻¹. The authors reported
5 an average biogas production of 15 L·d⁻¹, 20 L·d⁻¹ and 35 L·d⁻¹ at OLRs of 5.1 ± 0.1 kgCOD·m³·
6 d⁻¹, 8.1 ± 0.3 kgCOD·m³·d⁻¹ and 12.0 ± 0.2 kgCOD·m³·d⁻¹, respectively, with CH₄ content of
7 about 55%–65%. In addition, the reactor showed optimum COD removal efficiencies at 8 ± 0.3
8 kgCOD·m³·d⁻¹ OLR. In a recent study, the highest VFA yield (48.20 ± 1.21 mgVFA·10
9 mgCOD_{feed}⁻¹) was observed at OLR of 550 mgCOD·L⁻¹; however, the authors achieved less VFA
10 yield at the examined maximum OLR (715 mgCOD·L⁻¹), indicating that elevated OLRs can
11 lead to high VFA production but it is also crucial to optimize operating OLR during the
12 treatment of low strength wastewater in AnMBR [30]. In high-rate bioreactors such as UASB
13 and AnMBR, VFAs may not be efficiently converted to methane due to low-retention times
14 and can accumulate in the reactor and thus can be detected in the effluent [1,31]. In operating
15 conditions at elevated OLRs, VFAs should be therefore monitored to meet the local standards
16 for discharge or reuse.

17 **3.4. Effect of salinity in the system performance**

18 The impact of high salinity conditions was assessed in Period 4. Chloride concentration during
19 all operational periods are given in **Figure 5**. The red points mark the membrane cleaning days.
20 α value was stable around 0.3. Biogas production gradually decreased with increasing Cl⁻
21 concentrations (see **Figure 4**). Although the biogas production was 1.2-1.3 L·d⁻¹ during in the
22 beginning of Period 4 (so-called initial low saline conditions at 200 mgCl⁻·L⁻¹), it decreased to
23 0.13-0.57 L·d⁻¹ in the presence of 500 mgCl⁻·L⁻¹. When the Cl⁻ concentration was increased to
24 1500 mgL⁻¹ (at the end of Period 4), the CH₄ content in biogas reduced by 27% compared to
25 the reported values under low saline conditions. The CH₄ content of the biogas was adversely

1 affected (10%-20% in the beginning of Period 4 and 5% at the end) by high saline conditions.
2 The system almost failed to operate at the maximum examined Cl^- concentration (app. 2200
3 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), since the biogas production was $0.08 \text{ L}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$ with 3% CH_4 .
4 In line with the results of the current study, Aslan et al. [32] demonstrated that the COD removal
5 significantly decreased at about $20 \text{ gNa}^+\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ when treating saline wastewater in a UASB reactor.
6 Reduced biogas production and COD removal were also reported by Song et al. [12] in an
7 AnMBR operating under saline conditions $15 \text{ gNa}^+\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. A decrease in biomass production was
8 observed with the increase of salinity in the AnMBR. A NaCl shock load (increase from 5
9 $\text{gNaCl}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to $60 \text{ gNaCl}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) caused a reduction of COD and TKN removal efficiencies in the
10 study of Yogalakshmi et al. [17]; COD and TKN removal dropped to 64% and 23% at 60
11 $\text{gNaCl}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively, while the nitrification was completely inhibited. In the study of Luo et
12 al [33], a reduction of TOC and $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ removals was initially observed with elevated NaCl
13 loading; however, microbial diversity in saline AnMBR did not change and the adaptation of
14 microbial community to saline conditions was stated to recover AnMBR biological
15 performance. In a recent work of Muñoz Sierra et al. [34], the performance of UASB and
16 AnMBR was evaluated for the treatment of highly-saline phenolic wastewater. The authors
17 highlighted the superiority of AnMBR over UASB in terms of bioreactor conversion, biomass
18 characteristics and microbial community under salinity up to $26 \text{ gNa}^+\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ due to its greater
19 probability to maintain functionality and to respond to high salinity. In another study of the
20 same authors [18], a short-term salinity fluctuation of $18 \text{ gNa}^+\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to $20 \text{ gNa}^+\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ did not affect
21 the long term operation of AnMBR. The results indicated that high saline conditions initially
22 caused a decrease of the biological performance of AnMBR; however, long term adaptation of
23 microbial community to saline conditions (i.e. halotolerant or even halophilic microorganisms)
24 is required with high biomass concentrations for the system to regain its stability.

25 **3.5. Effect of OLR and high salinity on membrane operation**

1 The variations in the TMP value is shown in **Figure 6a**. The red points mark the membrane
2 cleaning days. The TMP of the membrane was stable at around 50 mbar when the system was
3 operated with methanol addition (Period 2, OLR of $2 \text{ kgCOD}\cdot\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$), with gas-sparging
4 condition of 10 seconds on and 120 seconds off. The specific flux normalized at 20°C was 175
5 $\text{L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{bar}^{-1}$ and only NaOCl cleaning was necessary after 50 days of operation. (**Figure 6b**)
6 During the fermentation liquid addition (Period 3, OLR of $2 \text{ kgCOD}\cdot\text{m}^3\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$) the behavior was
7 first similar to the methanol co-treatment; then the TMP increased gradually after 50 days of
8 operation and reached to 500 mbar after 100 days of operation. Thus, a more intense chemical
9 cleaning was applied to restore the initial permeability (citric acid at $1000 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) on day 315.
10 A significant EPS production was observed when the fermentation liquid was used, leading to
11 larger formation of the "cake" on the surface of the membrane. This was mainly due to the
12 fluctuation of the characteristics of the production of fermentation liquid. There was an increase
13 in EPS concentration from $52.8 \text{ mgEPS}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ in the Period 2 to $70.8 \text{ mgEPS}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ in the Period 3.
14 The latter decreased the membrane permeability a short time, higher rate pore obstruction and
15 therefore more intense and frequent cleaning was required.
16 In Period 4, the TMP remained stable at 12 mbar when the reactors were fed with the
17 fermentation liquid together with additional NaCl to increase salinity in the system, at the
18 concentration of $500 \text{ mgCl}^{-1}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The average TMP was around 50 mbar, at Cl^{-} concentration of
19 $1500 \text{ mgCl}^{-1}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, caused by the increased filtration resistance following the increased TMP due
20 to the increased EPS concentration in Period 3. The saline conditions therefore only affected
21 the initial TMP value and remained constant during the system operation.
22 The TMP of AnMBRs is highly dependent on the critical flux and the sparging rate together
23 with other environmental and operating conditions [35]. Furthermore, an initial flux below the
24 critical flux, prior to the introduction of peak flow, is reported to be advantageous to
25 permeability recovery [36]. In the study of Muñoz Sierra et al. [18], increased salt concentration

1 was found to affect the TMP negatively (350 mbar at a flux of $4.0 \text{ Lm}^2\text{h}^{-1}$). The deterioration
2 of membrane filtration performance was attributed to the decrease of biomass particle size when
3 salinity was increased. The small particle size had a significant influence on the cake layer
4 compaction that increased the operational values of the filtration resistance. Furthermore,
5 higher stability of process performances of AnMBR over UASB was reported to overcome high
6 salinity [34]. Elevated TMP values were also reported by Yurtsever et al. [19] with respect to
7 high salinity conditions. The salinity induced large molecules as foulants in gel/cake layer, that
8 may originate from biomass loosely bound EPS. The EPS properties are highly dependent on
9 the operating OLR [37]; and the OLR increase is often accompanied with high EPS production.

10 **3.6. Relationship between process parameters and system performance**

11 PCA was carried out to reveal the relationships between the applied operating conditions (i.e.
12 OLR, salinity) and system performance in terms of biogas production, CH_4 content of the
13 biogas, α value, TMP and J_s . The PCA supported our previous discussion regarding the
14 performance of the UASB+AnMBR system at different periods. OLR was closely grouped
15 together with the biogas production, CH_4 content and α value (**Figure 7**). This cluster showed
16 the close relationship between these parameters mostly in Period 1 which included only the
17 UASB operation. The data-points of Period 2 was comparatively more equally distributed
18 between the parameters; where the negative impacts of OLR on TMP were clearly reflected in
19 our data especially in Period 3. Furthermore, data points of Period 4 were characterized by high
20 chloride concentrations. The displayed negative correlation between the salinity and TMP
21 and/or J_s in Period 4 was due the citric acid cleaning of the membrane following the fouling
22 occurred in Period 3 that was previously mentioned. TMP value was close to its initial value
23 right after the citric acid cleaning and although TMP also slightly increased Period 4 at high
24 chloride concentrations (**see E-Supplementary material**), this increase was relatively low
25 comparing to Period 3.

1 3.7. Assessment of the possible re-use of the effluent

2 Population density and economic activity lead to significant differences in the water stress
3 levels of the basins. Water stress occurs in many areas of the EU, particularly in the
4 Mediterranean regions and part of the Atlantic regions. The data indicated by the European
5 Environment Agency regarding the use of water in various sectors indicate that irrigation in
6 agriculture represents about half of the water used annually with high seasonal and geographical
7 variations.

8 In May 2018, the European Commission presented a proposal for the reuse of treated
9 wastewater through a regulation that establishes common minimum requirements. This
10 proposal was going under revision with resolution of 12th February 2019. The proposal imposes
11 obligations that include:

- 12 • Compliance with the minimum requirements. These requirements differ based on four water
13 quality classes defined according to the type of crop and the irrigation method.
- 14 • Monitoring of recovered water based on minimum test frequency requirements.

15 The resolution also provides that the competent authorities of the member states can impose
16 additional requirements based on a risk management plan presented by the water utility to
17 mitigate unacceptable risks to health and environment.

18 In Italy, at national level, D.M. 185 of 2003 establishes the minimum quality requirements for
19 the reclaimed wastewater and its reuse, including limits on nitrogen and phosphorus.

20 The obtained effluent quality was compared against the values reported in **Table 4** (minimum
21 requirements for reuse). Analyzing the results obtained from this study, the UASB effluent is
22 not compliant with the limits required both by D.M. 185/03 and by the new EU proposal. The
23 permeate of the AnMBR appears of higher quality because it is free from TSS and falls into
24 class A since ultrafiltration guarantees also disinfection and *E. coli* removal. For the restrictions
25 posed by the D.M. 185/2003 for the reuse of the treated wastewater are mainly related to the

1 high concentration of chloride (High values are due to the salt water intrusion since the plant
2 is in a coastal area) and the nutrients concentration (N and P), both exceed the limit values. The
3 high nutrient content in the permeate (TN reaches a maximum value of $60 \text{ mgN}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, TP of 6
4 $\text{mgP}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), allows a potential reuse in fertigation field.

5 The national law in Italy is more restrictive compared to the new European proposal, which
6 introduces an innovative approach based on a framework for the risk management. EU
7 requirements vary according to the type of irrigated crops and according to the method of
8 irrigation, taking into account the potential risk of contamination of the products. The most
9 strict requirements are provided for class A, where reclaimed water can be in contact with the
10 edible parts of irrigated food crops.

11 **4. Conclusions**

12 Regarding the change of paradigm in the context of circular economy in terms of water,
13 nutrients and energy; site-specific optimization of an AnMBR is crucial especially in coastal
14 regions. In this particular study, the addition of fermented cellulosic sludge to raw wastewater
15 increased the biogas production without affecting the overall CH_4 content of the biogas. In case
16 of the application of the process in coastal areas, the biogas production decreased by 27% due
17 to the saline conditions when Cl^- concentration was up to $1500 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. Moreover, the CH_4
18 content of the biogas was also adversely related to the high saline conditions up to almost null
19 value for chloride higher than $2000 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. At Cl^- concentration less than $1500 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, long
20 term adaptation of microbial community (i.e. halotolerant or even halophilic microorganisms)
21 may be required with high biomass concentrations for the system to regain its stability and
22 recover the bioreactor performance in UASB+SuMBR. Concerning the membrane operation,
23 the increased salinity resulted only in the increase of initial TMP value where it stayed constant
24 during the following operating days. The AnMBR effluent fell into class A since ultrafiltration
25 guarantees also disinfection and *E. coli* removal.

1 **Acknowledgements**

2 This study was carried out within the framework of the “SMART-Plant” Innovation Action
3 which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation
4 programme under grant agreement No 690323. This study was carried out within “Safe and
5 Sustainable Solutions for the Integrated Use of Non-Conventional Water Resources in the
6 Mediterranean Agricultural Sector (FIT4REUSE)” which has received funding from the
7 Partnership on Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA) under grant
8 agreement number 1823 (Call 2018 Section 1 Water). The authors kindly acknowledge Diego
9 Cingolani, Gianluigi Buttiglieri and VivaServizi.

10 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

11 Supplementary data to this article can be found in the online version.

12 **References**

- 13 [1] V. Stazi, M.C. Tomei, Enhancing anaerobic treatment of domestic wastewater: State of
14 the art, innovative technologies and future perspectives, *Sci. Total Environ.* 635 (2018)
15 78–91. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.04.071.
- 16 [2] R. Pretel, F. Durán, A. Robles, M. V. Ruano, J. Ribes, J. Serralta, J. Ferrer, Designing
17 an AnMBR-based WWTP for energy recovery from urban wastewater: The role of
18 primary settling and anaerobic digestion, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 156 (2015) 132–139.
19 doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2015.09.047.
- 20 [3] J. Gouveia, F. Plaza, G. Garralon, F. Fdz-Polanco, M. Peña, Long-term operation of a
21 pilot scale anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) for the treatment of municipal
22 wastewater under psychrophilic conditions, *Bioresour. Technol.* 185 (2015) 225–233.
23 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2015.03.002.
- 24 [4] H. Ozgun, R.K. Dereli, M.E. Ersahin, C. Kinaci, H. Spanjers, J.B. Van Lier, A review
25 of anaerobic membrane bioreactors for municipal wastewater treatment: Integration

- 1 options, limitations and expectations, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 118 (2013) 89–104.
2 doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2013.06.036.
- 3 [5] R. Pretel, A. Robles, M. V. Ruano, A. Seco, J. Ferrer, Economic and environmental
4 sustainability of submerged anaerobic MBR-based (AnMBR-based) technology as
5 compared to aerobic-based technologies for moderate-/high-loaded urban wastewater
6 treatment, *J. Environ. Manage.* 166 (2016) 45–54. doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2015.10.004.
- 7 [6] J. Ferrer, R. Pretel, F. Durán, J.B. Giménez, A. Robles, M. V. Ruano, J. Serralta, J.
8 Ribes, A. Seco, Design methodology for submerged anaerobic membrane bioreactors
9 (AnMBR): A case study, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 141 (2015) 378–386.
10 doi:10.1016/j.seppur.2014.12.018.
- 11 [7] Ç. Akyol, A. Foglia, E.G. Ozbayram, N. Frison, E. Katsou, A.L. Eusebi, F. Fatone,
12 Validated innovative approaches for energy-efficient resource recovery and re-use
13 from municipal wastewater: From anaerobic treatment systems to a biorefinery
14 concept, *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 0 (2019) 1–34.
15 doi:10.1080/10643389.2019.1634456.
- 16 [8] R.Z. Gaur, A.A. Khan, B. Lew, V. Diamantis, A.A. Kazmi, Performance of Full-Scale
17 UASB Reactors Treating Low or Medium Strength Municipal Wastewater, *Environ.*
18 *Process.* 4 (2017) 137–146. doi:10.1007/s40710-017-0208-0.
- 19 [9] S.P. Lohani, S. Wang, S. Lackner, H. Horn, S.N. Khanal, R. Bakke, ADM1 modeling
20 of UASB treating domestic wastewater in Nepal, *Renew. Energy.* 95 (2016) 263–268.
21 doi:10.1016/j.renene.2016.04.014.
- 22 [10] T. Niwa, M. Hatamoto, T. Yamashita, H. Noguchi, O. Takase, K.A. Kekre, W.S. Ang,
23 G. Tao, H. Seah, T. Yamaguchi, Demonstration of a full-scale plant using an UASB
24 followed by a ceramic MBR for the reclamation of industrial wastewater, *Bioresour.*
25 *Technol.* 218 (2016) 1–8. doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2016.06.036.

- 1 [11] R.K. Dereli, M.E. Ersahin, H. Ozgun, I. Ozturk, D. Jeison, F. van der Zee, J.B. van
2 Lier, Potentials of anaerobic membrane bioreactors to overcome treatment limitations
3 induced by industrial wastewaters, *Bioresour. Technol.* 122 (2012) 160–170.
4 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2012.05.139.
- 5 [12] X. Song, J. McDonald, W.E. Price, S.J. Khan, F.I. Hai, H.H. Ngo, W. Guo, L.D.
6 Nghiem, Effects of salinity build-up on the performance of an anaerobic membrane
7 bioreactor regarding basic water quality parameters and removal of trace organic
8 contaminants, *Bioresour. Technol.* 216 (2016) 399–405.
9 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2016.05.075.
- 10 [13] C. Shin, J. Bae, Current status of the pilot-scale anaerobic membrane bioreactor
11 treatments of domestic wastewaters: A critical review, *Bioresour. Technol.* 247 (2018)
12 1038–1046. doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2017.09.002.
- 13 [14] B.Q. Liao, J.T. Kraemer, D.M. Bagley, Anaerobic membrane bioreactors: Applications
14 and research directions, *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 36 (2006) 489–530.
15 doi:10.1080/10643380600678146.
- 16 [15] Y. Jeong, S.W. Hermanowicz, C. Park, Treatment of food waste recycling wastewater
17 using anaerobic ceramic membrane bioreactor for biogas production in mainstream
18 treatment process of domestic wastewater, *Water Res.* 123 (2017) 86–95.
19 doi:10.1016/j.watres.2017.06.049.
- 20 [16] G. Skouteris, D. Hermosilla, P. Lopez, C. Negro, A. Blanco, Anaerobic membrane
21 bioreactors for wastewater treatment: A review, *Chem. Eng. Journal* 198–199
22 (2012) 138–148. doi:10.1016/j.cej.2012.05.070.
- 23 [17] K.N. Yogalakshmi, K. Joseph, Effect of transient sodium chloride shock loads on the
24 performance of submerged membrane bioreactor, *Bioresour. Technol.* 101 (2010)
25 7054–7061. doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2010.03.135.

- 1 [18] J.D. Muñoz Sierra, M.J. Oosterkamp, W. Wang, H. Spanjers, J.B. van Lier, Impact of
2 long-term salinity exposure in anaerobic membrane bioreactors treating phenolic
3 wastewater: Performance robustness and endured microbial community, *Water Res.*
4 141 (2018) 172–184. doi:10.1016/j.watres.2018.05.006.
- 5 [19] A. Yurtsever, B. Calimlioglu, M. Görür, Ö. Çinar, E. Sahinkaya, Effect of NaCl
6 concentration on the performance of sequential anaerobic and aerobic membrane
7 bioreactors treating textile wastewater, *Chem. Eng. J.* 287 (2016) 456–465.
8 doi:10.1016/j.cej.2015.11.061.
- 9 [20] J. Yang, H. Spanjers, D. Jeison, J.B. Van Lier, Impact of Na⁺ on biological wastewater
10 treatment and the potential of anaerobic membrane bioreactors: A review, *Crit. Rev.*
11 *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 43 (2013) 2722–2746. doi:10.1080/10643389.2012.694335.
- 12 [21] S. Palmieri, G. Cipolletta, C. Pastore, C. Giosuè, Ç. Akyol, A.L. Eusebi, N. Frison, F.
13 Tittarelli, F. Fatone, Pilot scale cellulose recovery from sewage sludge and reuse in
14 building and construction material, *Waste Manag.* 100 (2019) 208–218.
15 doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2019.09.015.
- 16 [22] K.M. Wang, D. Cingolani, A.L. Eusebi, A. Soares, B. Jefferson, E.J. McAdam,
17 Identification of gas sparging regimes for granular anaerobic membrane bioreactor to
18 enable energy neutral municipal wastewater treatment, *J. Memb. Sci.* 555 (2018) 125–
19 133. doi:10.1016/j.memsci.2018.03.032.
- 20 [23] APHA/AWWA/WEF, Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and
21 Wastewater, *Stand. Methods.* (2012) 541. doi:ISBN 9780875532356.
- 22 [24] A. Hussain, S.K. Dubey, Specific methanogenic activity test for anaerobic degradation
23 of influents, *Appl. Water Sci.* 7 (2017) 535–542. doi:10.1007/s13201-015-0305-z.
- 24 [25] X. Zhang, P.L. Bishop, B.K. Kinkle, Comparison of extraction methods for quantifying
25 extracellular polymers in biofilms, *Water Sci. Technol.* 39 (1999) 211–218.

- 1 doi:10.1016/S0273-1223(99)00170-5.
- 2 [26] V. Vasilaki, E.I.P. Volcke, A.K. Nandi, M.C.M. van Loosdrecht, E. Katsou, Relating
3 N₂O emissions during biological nitrogen removal with operating conditions using
4 multivariate statistical techniques, *Water Res.* 140 (2018) 387–402.
5 doi:10.1016/j.watres.2018.04.052.
- 6 [27] M.D. Seib, K.J. Berg, D.H. Zitomer, Low energy anaerobic membrane bioreactor for
7 municipal wastewater treatment, *J. Memb. Sci.* 514 (2016) 450–457.
8 doi:10.1016/j.memsci.2016.05.007.
- 9 [28] C.H. Wei, M. Harb, G. Amy, P.Y. Hong, T.O. Leiknes, Sustainable organic loading
10 rate and energy recovery potential of mesophilic anaerobic membrane bioreactor for
11 municipal wastewater treatment, *Bioresour. Technol.* 166 (2014) 326–334.
12 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2014.05.053.
- 13 [29] K.C. Wijekoon, C. Visvanathan, A. Abeynayaka, Effect of organic loading rate on
14 VFA production, organic matter removal and microbial activity of a two-stage
15 thermophilic anaerobic membrane bioreactor, *Bioresour. Technol.* 102 (2011) 5353–
16 5360. doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2010.12.081.
- 17 [30] M.A. Khan, H.H. Ngo, W. Guo, Y. Liu, L.D. Nghiem, S.W. Chang, D.D. Nguyen, S.
18 Zhang, G. Luo, H. Jia, Optimization of hydraulic retention time and organic loading
19 rate for volatile fatty acid production from low strength wastewater in an anaerobic
20 membrane bioreactor, *Bioresour. Technol.* 271 (2019) 100–108.
21 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2018.09.075.
- 22 [31] L. Zhang, J. De Vrieze, T.L.G. Hendrickx, W. Wei, H. Temmink, H. Rijnaarts, G.
23 Zeeman, Anaerobic treatment of raw domestic wastewater in a UASB-digester at 10 °C
24 and microbial community dynamics, *Chem. Eng. J.* 334 (2018) 2088–2097.
25 doi:10.1016/j.cej.2017.11.073.

- 1 [32] S. Aslan, N. Şekerdağ, Salt inhibition on anaerobic treatment of high salinity
2 wastewater by upflow anaerobic sludge blanket (UASB) reactor, *Desalin. Water Treat.*
3 57 (2016) 12998–13004. doi:10.1080/19443994.2015.1059369.
- 4 [33] W. Luo, H. V. Phan, F.I. Hai, W.E. Price, W. Guo, H.H. Ngo, K. Yamamoto, L.D.
5 Nghiem, Effects of salinity build-up on the performance and bacterial community
6 structure of a membrane bioreactor, *Bioresour. Technol.* 200 (2016) 305–310.
7 doi:10.1016/j.biortech.2015.10.043.
- 8 [34] J.D. Muñoz Sierra, M.J. Oosterkamp, W. Wang, H. Spanjers, J.B. van Lier,
9 Comparative performance of upflow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor and anaerobic
10 membrane bioreactor treating phenolic wastewater: Overcoming high salinity, *Chem.*
11 *Eng. J.* 366 (2019) 480–490. doi:10.1016/j.cej.2019.02.097.
- 12 [35] R.A. Fox, D.C. Stuckey, The effect of sparging rate on transmembrane pressure and
13 critical flux in an AnMBR, *J. Environ. Manage.* 151 (2015) 280–285.
14 doi:10.1016/j.jenvman.2014.08.011.
- 15 [36] K.M. Wang, B. Jefferson, A. Soares, E.J. McAdam, Sustaining membrane permeability
16 during unsteady-state operation of anaerobic membrane bioreactors for municipal
17 wastewater treatment following peak-flow, *J. Memb. Sci.* 564 (2018) 289–297.
18 doi:10.1016/j.memsci.2018.07.032.
- 19 [37] R. Chen, Y. Nie, Y. Hu, R. Miao, T. Utashiro, Q. Li, M. Xu, Y.Y. Li, Fouling
20 behaviour of soluble microbial products and extracellular polymeric substances in a
21 submerged anaerobic membrane bioreactor treating low-strength wastewater at room
22 temperature, *J. Memb. Sci.* 531 (2017) 1–9. doi:10.1016/j.memsci.2017.02.046.
23
24
25

1 **Figure Captions**

2 **Fig. 1.** Salt water intrusion (European Environment Agency, 2017) and the location of
3 Falconara Marittima WWTP.

4 **Fig. 2.** Scheme of the UASB pilot plant coupled with anaerobic ultrafiltration membranes:
5 Configuration with a) urban wastewater, b) co-treatment of urban wastewater and methanol, c)
6 co-treatment of urban wastewater and fermentation liquid.

7 **Fig. 3.** Variations in a) OLR b) α value (the ratio of partial alkalinity over total alkalinity) at
8 different periods of the operational time.

9 **Fig. 4.** Variations in a) Biogas production b) CH₄ content of the biogas at different periods of
10 the operational time.

11 **Fig. 5.** Variations in chloride concentration at different periods of the operational time.

12 **Fig. 6.** Variations in a) TMP profile b) Specific flux at 20°C in AnMBR at different periods of
13 the operational time. The red points mark the membrane cleaning days. Citric acid cleaning
14 was conducted on day 315. TMP and specific flux were not recorded between the days 315
15 and 432.

16 **Fig. 7.** Principal component analysis (PCA) of the operating parameters and system
17 performance.

a

a

a

PCA - Biplot

Table 1. Characterization of the raw wastewater that enters the WWTP of Falconara Marittima in dry weather.

Q _{in}	pH	Conductivity	COD	TSS	NH ₄ -N	TN	TP	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	PO ₄ -P	Na ⁺	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺
m ³ ·d ⁻¹	-	μS·cm ⁻¹	mg·L ⁻¹	mg·L ⁻¹	mg·L ⁻¹	mg·L ⁻¹	mg·L ⁻¹						
19525±2488	7.7±0.2	1480±150	373±148	232±110	31±6	38±7	5.1±1.5	334±236	135±52	2.7±0.6	160.1±36	26±4.8	125±9

Table 2. Configurations and operational parameters in each period.

Feed	Configuration	Period	Duration time	OLR	HRT	v_{upflow}	Temperature
			d	$\text{kgCOD m}^{-3}\text{d}^{-1}$	h	m h^{-1}	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
Urban	UASB	1	156	1	5	1	30
Urban + Methanol	UASB	2.1	90	2	5	1	30
Urban + Methanol	UASB+AnMBR	2.2	50	2	5	1	30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ UASB+ ambient anMBR
Urban + Methanol	UASB+AnMBR	2.3	33	2	5	1	30
Urban + fermentation liquid	UASB+AnMBR	3	141	2	5	1	30
Urban + fermentation liquid+ salinity	UASB+AnMBR	4	63	2	5	1	30

Table 3. Influent characterization in each period.

Parameter	Unit	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4
pH	-	7.8 ± 0.2	7.5 ± 0.3	7.6 ± 0.2	7.7 ± 0.2
Alkalinity	mg·L ⁻¹	281 ± 92	393 ± 76	526 ± 110	405 ± 41
EC	μS·cm ⁻¹	1464 ± 153	1467 ± 380	1817 ± 350	2787 ± 1300
Cl	mg·L ⁻¹	282 ± 126	304 ± 300	393 ± 377	1100 ± 618
COD	mg·L ⁻¹	207 ± 73	388 ± 80	375 ± 148	550 ± 330
sCOD	mg·L ⁻¹	50 ± 24	242 ± 55	250 ± 140	297 ± 198
TN	mg·L ⁻¹	35.8 ± 16	30.5 ± 8	78.8 ± 35	-
NH ₄ ⁺ -N	mg·L ⁻¹	22 ± 6	20.5 ± 6	61 ± 33	30 ± 10
TP	mg·L ⁻¹	4.2 ± 1.1	2.6 ± 1.1	7.8 ± 4.8	-
PO ₄ -P	mg·L ⁻¹	2.3 ± 0.9	1.69 ± 0.8	5.3 ± 3.9	4.5 ± 4
TSS	mg·L ⁻¹	202 ± 176	106 ± 50	168 ± 147	210 ± 100

Table 4. Reuse limit values and comparison with pilot system effluent.

		Italian National Decree 185 of 2003					EU RESOLUTION on minimum requirements for water reuse, February 2019					
Parameters	Unit of measure	IRRIGATION	CLASS A	CLASS B	CLASS C	CLASS D	UASB EFFLUENT UWW feeding	UASB EFFLUENT UWW+M feeding	UASB EFFLUENT UWW+F feeding	PERMEATE UWW+M feeding	PERMEATE UWW+F feeding	
		Limit Value	Limit Value	Limit Value	Limit Value	Limit Value	Average Value	Average Value	Average Value	Average Value	Average Value	
Turbidity	NTU	-	≤5	-	-	-						
ph	-	6-9.5 (note1)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	7.9 ± 0.2	7.5 ± 0.3	8.02 ± 0.2	7.93 ± 0.2	8.2 ± 0.2	
TSS	mgL ⁻¹	10	≤10	35	35	35	26.57 ± 12.8	51.3 ± 57.2	183.41 ± 118.4	0	0	
BOD ₅	mgO ₂ L ⁻¹	20	≤10	25	25	25						
COD	mgO ₂ L ⁻¹	100	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	81.67 ± 28	107.7 ± 63.7	303.28 ± 117.6	74.69 ± 71	77.4 ± 87.8	
Total Phosphorus	mgPL ⁻¹	2 (note2)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	3.83 ± 0.8	3 ± 1.5	6.96 ± 6.8	2.43 ± 1	6 ± 4.3	
Total Nitrogen	mgN·L ⁻¹	15 (note2)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	30.46	30.1	78.15 ± 44.8	26.32	60.2	
Nitrate	mgN·L ⁻¹	-	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	0.16 ± 0.53	0.017 ± 0.02	0	0.016 ± 0.027	0.018 ± 0.012	
Ammonia Nitrogen	mgNH ₄ ⁺ L ⁻¹	2 (note1)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	34.04 ± 7.3	32.9 ± 13.1	78.15 ± 44.8	29.86 ± 9.3	64.88 ± 52.62	
Electric Conductivity	µS·cm ⁻¹	3000 (note3)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	1606 ± 705	1497.5 ± 528	1832.33 ± 401.4	1880.8 ± 1323.1	1737.7 ± 375.9	
Chlorides	mgCl·L ⁻¹	250 (note1)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	315.98 ± 207	275 ± 104.7	386 ± 380	508.75 ± 331	373.2 ± 367.9	
Fluorides	mgF·L ⁻¹	1.5	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)						
Sulphates	mgSO ₄ L ⁻¹	500 (note1)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	(note 6)	184 ± 99	66.2 ± 35.7	80.85 ± 64.7	72.13 ± 62.2	57.3 ± 32.5	
Microbiological parameters	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	UFC in 100 mL	10 (note 4)	≤10	≤100	≤1000	≤10000				1	
	<i>Salmonella</i>		Absent (note5)									
	Helminth	Eggs in 100 mL	-		≤1	≤1	≤1					
	LOG Reduction <i>E.coli</i>	-		≥5	-	-	-				4.71	

LEGEND: UWW=urban wastewater, M=methanol, F=fermentation liquid;

NOTES: 1) guide values, regions may authorize different limits, 2) up to 10 mg P/L and up to 35 mg N/L for irrigation use in non-vulnerable areas, 3) guide values, but 4000 is the maximum permissible, 4) for 80% of samples, 100 UFC/ml 100 is the maximum value and for water impoundment or phytoremediation apply the limits of 50 (80% of the samples) and 200 UFC /ml 100 (punctual maximum value), 5) for 100% of samples, 6) limit value not provided.

SUPPLEMENTARY FILE

Long-term operation of a pilot-scale anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) treating high salinity low loaded municipal wastewater in real environment

Alessia Foglia¹, Çağrı Akyol^{1*}, Nicola Frison², Evina Katsou³, Anna Laura Eusebi^{1*},
Francesco Fatone¹

¹ *Department of Science and Engineering of Materials, Environment and Urban Planning-SIMAU, Faculty of Engineering, Marche Polytechnic University, 60131, Ancona, Italy*

² *Department of Biotechnology, University of Verona, 37134, Verona, Italy*

³ *Department of Civil Engineering and Environmental Engineering, Institute of Environment, Health and Societies, Brunel University London, Uxbridge Campus, Middlesex, UB8 3PH, Uxbridge, United Kingdom*

* Corresponding author (Ç. Akyol)

E-mail: c.akyol@staff.univpm.it

Tel: +39 071 2204911 Fax: +39 071 2204729

Table S1. Operational parameters during AnMBR the start-up period.

Input flow rate	Q_{in}	L/h	3
Time on	on	min	9
Time off	off	min	1
Cycle time	t	min	10
$Q_{backflush}$	Q_b	L/h	5.8
$Q_{medium\ permeate\ flow}$	Q_p	L/h	3.2
Maximum pressure	TMP_{max}	mbar	600
Minimum pressure	TMP_{min}	mbar	-600
Gas sparging on	N_2 on	s	10
Gas sparging off	N_2 off	s	120
$Q_{Nitrogen}$	Q_{N2}	m^3/h	1

Fig. S1. Critical flux of the membrane.

Fig. S2. Increase of TMP without gas-sparging.

Fig. S3. TMP values with gas-sparging.

Fig. S4. Gas sparging frequency and % degassed CH₄.

Fig. S5. Gas sparging frequency and % degassed CH₄.

Fig. S6. TMP values in Period 4 with respect to increasing chloride concentrations.

Table S2. PCA loadings.

Variable	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4	PC5	PC6	PC7
OLR	-0,1838845	-0,3262092	0,71934166	-0,41077103	0,32670591	-0,20072177	0,16298097
Salinity	0,4745915	-0,1742411	0,23456583	0,5472497	-0,16098917	-0,24544	0,5511273
a	-0,1781115	-0,6476819	-0,1547099	0,3949512	0,39876817	0,45428528	-0,05892063
Biogas	-0,3961042	-0,2996411	0,23894083	0,07928107	-0,81264309	0,12845989	-0,11422693
CH ₄	-0,4636634	-0,2018725	-0,40277445	0,11071456	0,06304102	-0,74767461	0,08238478
TMP	-0,2944141	0,4331674	0,42594414	0,59757857	0,20353572	-0,09881501	-0,36873654
Js	0,5006634	-0,3543508	0,05331894	-0,01245492	-0,0503977	-0,32834613	-0,71443865